

USING COMPUTER AND ONLINE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Introduction. The integration of computer and online technology has had a tremendous impact on my educational path as a student negotiating the complex terrain of English language learning. The classroom is becoming more virtual than it was in the past due to the advent of immersive digital experiences that replace the old chalk-and-talk method. I discuss how these digital tools have changed my learning process and the way I interact with the English language in this piece, offering my thoughts into the dynamic fusion of technology and English language training.

The digital revolution in education involves redefining the learning environment rather than just replacing pen and paper with keyboards and computers. My journey takes me from interactive learning platforms to artificial intelligence (AI)-powered language examinations, all taking place in a world where English grammar and vocabulary subtleties meet with bits and pixels. This is a transformation of my learning process, not merely a leap in technology.

Body:

1. ****Interactive Learning Platforms: A Classroom Beyond Walls:****

The development of interactive learning platforms has been a major turning point in my digital path. These platforms provide a dynamic environment where learning turns into a cooperative, interactive project, going beyond the boundaries of conventional classrooms. My comprehension of the English language has changed as a result of participating in online forums, having virtual conversations with peers, and having access to multimedia resources. These activities have created a lively and interactive learning environment.

2. ****AI-Powered Language Assessments: A Personalized Learning Compass:****

For me, the addition of artificial intelligence to language evaluations has changed everything. Artificial intelligence-powered tests, in contrast to traditional examinations that seemed to take a one-size-fits-all approach, precisely identify my skills and shortcomings. In addition to directing my

learning process, the tailored feedback gives me the ability to concentrate on particular facets of language learning, turning tests from insignificant examinations into priceless educational opportunities.

3. ****E-Libraries and Digital Resources: A Gateway to Infinite Knowledge:****

My access to English language resources has greatly increased as a result of the digitization of libraries and educational materials. My travelling companions on my language adventure are interactive multimedia resources, e-books, and internet articles. The digital library offers me the freedom to explore the extensive fields of English literature and language studies at my own convenience and leisure because it is not limited by physical location or business hours.

4. ****Language Apps: Gamifying Learning for Fun and Fluency:****

Apps for learning languages add a gamification element to my experience, making the process of learning vocabulary and grammar exciting and fun. With their interactive tests and language games, these apps add an entertaining and engaging element to learning. My desire to get better is fueled by the competitive aspects, which produce a positive feedback loop that promotes regular interaction with English-language content.

5. ****Virtual Writing Labs: Crafting Proficiency in a Digital Workshop:****

These days, I can refine my writing abilities with digital assistance in virtual writing labs, which have replaced physical workshops. Grammar mistakes are fixed by AI-powered tools, which also provide recommendations for improving style and clarity. This real-time feedback encourages me to write more iteratively, which helps me improve my storytelling and expression skills and raises my overall written English proficiency.

6. Digital Literacy for Language Navigators:

The acquisition of digital literacy has become inseparable from language learning in this age of rapid technological evolution. My journey as a student navigating this digital linguascape involves not only improving my language skills but also learning how to critically navigate the enormous digital information repository. My language education now includes teaching me how to identify trustworthy sources, assess online material, and use digital communication responsibly.

7. Online Language Communities: Crafting a Global Discourse:

My experience with digital languages goes beyond traditional classroom settings to include virtual language communities. I now have a virtual space to interact with other language enthusiasts around the world thanks to platforms

like social media language learning groups and language exchange forums. Through this in-the-moment communication, I have gained a deeper comprehension of cultural subtleties, idiomatic expressions, and colloquial usage—all of which contribute to a feeling of community that is not limited by geography.

8. Multimodal Expression through Digital Storytelling:

One increasingly useful tool in my linguistic toolbox is digital storytelling. Multimedia platforms give me more creative freedom to express myself than just writing assignments by combining text, images, and audio. By allowing me to create narratives that resonate through a variety of sensory channels and transcend the limitations of conventional linguistic expression, this multimodal approach not only fosters my creativity but also allows me to explore language in a more holistic way.

9. Language Learning Analytics: Navigating Personal Progress:

Using analytics tools for language learning has completely changed how I monitor and analyse my development. These resources offer valuable information about my study habits, my strong points, and possible areas for development. My learning trajectory becomes more evident when I use analytics to visualise my linguistic journey, which enables me to develop more intelligent and flexible study techniques.

10. Augmented Reality Adventures in Language Exploration:

My journey with digital language has been made even more exciting by augmented reality (AR). Applications for augmented reality (AR) superimpose digital data on the real environment to make language learning more engaging. These augmented reality adventures, which range from interactive vocabulary lessons to virtual language scavenger hunts, add a playful element to the learning process and transform my surroundings into a blank canvas for language exploration.

Conclusion. I have found that my experience with technology-infused language learning has been nothing short of revolutionary in terms of navigating the complex world of the digital linguascope. Every digital aspect, from augmented reality experiences to algorithmic syntax, has woven itself into the fabric of my linguistic exploration, upending preconceived notions and bringing in a new age of unimaginable possibilities.

Technology and language learning combined are not a replacement, but rather an enhancement that combines the old with the new and the real with the virtual. Online communities, digital literacy, and language learning analytics

have all grown to be indispensable allies that have helped me navigate the intricacies of the digital age and maintain a feeling of interconnectedness throughout the world.

To sum up, my journey through digital language goes beyond the confines of traditional education and becomes a vibrant story of development, connection, and exploration. The incorporation of technology into language learning does not take the place of language acquisition; rather, it pushes language learning into new frontiers, allowing learners like myself to explore, discover, and accept the constantly changing environment where language and technology meet. Not only is the digital age changing the way I learn English, but it's also making me an expert user of the digital linguascape, where the opportunities are as endless as the virtual world's boundaries.

References:

1. Warschauer, M. (2003). *Technology and Social Inclusion: Rethinking the Digital Divide*. MIT Press.
2. Chik, A., & Moyer, M. (2018). *Language Learning Beyond the Classroom: Exploring Digitally-Mediated Immersion*. Routledge.
3. Liaw, M.-L. (2006). E-learning and the Development of Intercultural Competence. *Language Learning & Technology*, 10(3), 49–64.
4. Reinders, H., & Wattana, S. (2014). *Learn English or Die: The Effects of Digital Games on Interaction and Willingness to Communicate in a Foreign Language*. *Digital Culture & Education*, 6(1), 4–29.
5. Flowerdew, J., & Miller, L. (2005). *Second Language Listening: Theory and Practice*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Belz, J. A., & Kinginger, C. (2003). Discourse Options and the Development of Pragmatic Competence by Classroom Learners of German: The Case of Address Forms. *Language Learning*, 53(4), 591–647.
7. Жамолиддинова, М. (2022). Обучение английскому языку посредством современных технологий. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 29, 321-324.
8. Жамолиддинова, М. (2023). Олий ўқув юртларида нофилологик чет тили ўқитишни ташкил қилиш ва талабалар нутқ бирликларини ассоциатив йўналишда тадбиқ этиш. *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(3), 12-14.
9. Jamoliddinova, Mohinur Davlatjonovna (2023). “Adekvatlik” va “ekvivalentlik” konsepsiyasining o’zaro bog’liq xususiyatlarini takomillashtirish.

Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3 (6), 944-947.

10. Jamoliddinova Mohinur (2023). Чет тилини ўқитишда коммуникатив - дидактик ўйинларнинг аҳамияти. Yangi O'zbekistonning iqtisodiy taraqqiyotida tarmoq va hududlarni rivojlantirish istiqbollari mavzusidagi ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya, pp.57-58.